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Nonlinearly elastic and anisotropic constitutive model for ePTFE vascular graft based on tensile and inflation experiments

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ABSTRACT

The long-term success of interventions in cardiovascular medicine can be enhanced by the computer-assisted planning of these procedures. However, the reliability of all computational simulations depends significantly on the input parameters. One of the most important is the constitutive model for the biological tissue and for the implant material. While the last few decades have brought great advances in modeling the mechanical properties of the arterial wall, synthetic grafts have not received as much attention. The primary goal of our research is to contribute to filling this gap. Our study is focused on determining a constitutive model for ePTFE vascular grafts. Uniaxial tensile experiments with strips cut from tubular vascular grafts SA1802 (Gore-Tex Stretch Vascular Graft – Large diameter) in the circumferential and longitudinal direction, and pressurization experiments with intact graft tubes V06010L (Gore-Tex Vascular Graft – Standard-walled) were carried out. A nonlinearly elastic anisotropic model was used to describe the mechanical response observed in these experiments. The four-fiber hyperelastic model based on the exponential function combined with the neo-Hookean term was able to fit the data observed in both the uniaxial tensile and inflation-extension experiments with one single set of parameters. Thus, the resulting model is suitable to be used in numerical simulations studying surgical procedures involving ePTFE vascular grafts in the mechanical states of uniaxial as well as multiaxial stress.

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1. Introduction

Vascular diseases such as coronary heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, and peripheral artery disease, are the leading cause of mortality worldwide [1, 2]. Advances in cardiovascular medicine have broadened the spectrum of cardiovascular conditions that can be treated with surgery or other methods, leading to an increase in the number of medical interventions performed every year [3]. While autologous grafts remain the preferred choice in coronary artery [4] and peripheral artery bypass [5], their unavailability may necessitate the need for a substitute. Furthermore, artificially made grafts may be the only option for replacement in cases of large-artery reconstructions in which an autologous vessel cannot be deployed due to the difference in diameter [6].

Over the past few years, the possibility of the usage of tissue-engineered vascular grafts has been extensively studied [7, 8]. Progress in novel manufacturing techniques such as 3D printing, electrospinning and extrusion, as well as the development of various materials such as polycaprolactone or polylactic acid paves the way for biodegradable vascular replacements to be utilized in the future [9–13]. However,

artificial grafts still remain the gold standard in bypass surgery if an autologous vessel cannot be used. Synthetic grafts are also usually the only choice for reconstructive surgeries of the aorta, arch vessels, and common femoral artery [14]. Furthermore, they are essential in many types of shunting vascular surgeries in which a connection is made between two blood vessels. Polymer grafts are used, for example, to create a link between the carotid and pulmonary artery in order to increase the blood flow to the lungs in the Blalock-Taussing shunt [15]. Moreover, artificial grafts play a key role in creating vascular access for hemodialysis in patients with end-stage renal diseases. Preferably, a fistula is created directly between a vein and an artery to increase the blood flow through the vein in order to make the dialytic process possible [16]. However, if the arteriovenous fistula cannot be created directly, a graft is used to connect the vessels with synthetic grafts. This method has shown good results, as outlined for example, by Driessen et al. [17].

Currently, there are two polymer materials predominantly used in vascular surgery – polyethylene terephthalate (PET), also produced under the brand name Dacron, and expanded polytetrafluorethylene (ePTFE), also found under the brand names

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Gore and Gore-Tex. These materials find their use as coating layers of metallic stents [18], replacements in reconstructive surgery [19], grafts in coronary bypass surgery [20], components of stent-grafts in endovascular aneurysm repair of the abdominal aorta [21], shunting conduits [17] and, although not preferable, grafts in peripheral artery bypass surgeries [22].

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and fluid-structure interaction (FSI) simulations are invaluable in describing the mechanobiological interactions that can lead to pathologies within the cardiovascular system. They could potentially be employed to help determine the outcomes of various vascular diseases and assist in clinicians' decision making, helping them to select the right treatment of the illness, provided a high quality of input data is supplied to the computational software. Nowadays, simulations are frequently used to predict and possibly improve the performance of medical treatments, devices, grafts, and implants [23–25]. In particular, wall shear stress is known to be a key factor behind the development of intimal hyperplasia, atherosclerosis, and thrombosis, which are frequent causes of graft failure [24–26]. CFD simulations aimed at describing the wall shear stress in the vascular prosthesis and its adjacent vessels are thus common in the literature. For example, CFD has been used to highlight the advantages of unconventional surgical approaches such as Miller's cuffs [27] or the fenestration technique of stent-grafting [28]. Computational simulations are also crucial in optimizing the performance of arteriovenous shunts for vascular access [29].

The accuracy and reliability of a graft-vessel interaction simulation is strongly dependent on the material characteristics that are assigned to the vessels and the graft. Usually, there are four levels on which the mechanics can be modeled. The simplest approach is to assume fully rigid walls for the tubes. This approximation is usually done only for the artificial grafts, as they are much stiffer than arteries and veins [30]. However, for more accurate results it is necessary to account for the distensibility of the grafts, which can be done within the framework of linear or nonlinear elasticity as the material exhibits little dissipation after it has been preconditioned. However, a more complex constitutive relationship may be necessary if one's aim is to assess the nonelastic behavior of the material, for example due to damage under overload stress. Whichever approach is chosen, an anisotropic model should be employed since the material exhibits different properties in the longitudinal and circumferential direction. The choice of the model complexity is a tradeoff between the computational time and the accuracy of the simulation, with each of the mentioned approaches having been described in the literature [31–33]. However, Jayendiran et al. [34] showed that choosing a hyperelastic model for an aortic PET graft instead of a linear elastic one led to a significantly different outcome of the simulation, suggesting that employing a suitable nonlinear constitutive model would lead to more reliable results.

The main reason linear elasticity or rigid body approximation is often chosen over nonlinear anisotropic elasticity in simulations of synthetic grafts is the lack of data on the material properties of the replacements. While there exist publications describing the mechanical properties of both PET and ePTFE in general [35, 36], only a very limited number of them

deal with the constitutive modeling of a vascular prosthesis made from these materials. In that sense, PET grafts seem to have received more scientific attention. Constitutive modeling of Dacron grafts was done by Bustos et al. [37, 38] who fitted an anisotropic hyperelastic model to the experimental data from uniaxial tensile and inflation-extension experiments. Furthermore, Amabili et al. [39, 40] fitted a viscoelastic model to data from the above-mentioned types of experiments carried out with PET grafts. Papers dealing with the constitutive modeling of ePTFE grafts are, however, much more limited. Faturechi et al. [41] model a Gore-Tex vascular graft employing a viscoelastic model identified under uniaxial stress conditions. However, the model used is isotropic, which contradicts the initial impression one gets when handling commercially available synthetic vascular replacements. One immediately finds that the grafts can be easily stretched to length, but that they have very limited circumferential distensibility. In fact, adjusting this asymmetric stiffness toward values close to the biomechanics of biological arteries has been a goal of research and development for several decades. The same drawback can be attributed to the paper by Kuchumov et al. [42] who also employ an isotropic hyperelastic model to describe the mechanics of an ePTFE graft. Moreover, based on the stress-strain response depicted in the article, the constitutive-parameter value combination seems to result in a materially unstable model, limiting its usability. García-García et al. [43] employ an anisotropic hyperelastic model to describe the response of Gore-Tex abdominal patches. Nevertheless, to the best of the authors' knowledge, a work that would provide an anisotropic hyperelastic constitutive description of the mechanical response of ePTFE vascular grafts is not available in the literature.

This study aims to fill the gap that seems to remain in the field of the mechanics of synthetic vascular grafts. Inflation experiments under physiological pressure loading and uniaxial tensile tests involving overloading were performed with Gore-Tex vascular grafts. An anisotropic, hyperelastic, four-fiber family model of the exponential type was used to fit the experimental data. The model was capable of fitting the mechanical response obtained at both loading conditions. The resulting constitutive parameters can be used in simulations concerning the hemodynamics of Gore-Tex grafts and their interactions with adjacent blood vessels.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples for mechanical testing

The ePTFE vascular replacements manufactured by W. L. Gore & Associates, Inc. (Delaware, USA) were purchased from a local distributor (Meditrade spol. s r.o., Czech Republic). These were grafts sold by the manufacturer as V06010L (small-diameter standard wall) and SA1802 (large-diameter standard wall). Samples for the inflation-extension experiment were cut from V06010L grafts whereas strips for uniaxial tensile tests were prepared from SA1802 grafts. Inflation-extension experiments were conducted with cylindrical tubes measuring 60 mm in length, 3 mm in radius, and 0.5 mm in thickness. The strips for tensile tests had dimensions of 30 mm in length, 4 mm in width, and 0.9 mm

in thickness and were cut from the graft in both the longitudinal and circumferential directions. Figure 1 illustrates a sample for the inflation experiment and a tensile test sample.

2.2. Uniaxial tensile test

The tensile tests were conducted on a multipurpose testing machine (Zwick/Roell, Germany) fitted with a built-in video-extensometer and electromechanical actuators for loading up to 100 N. HBM U9C force transducers (Hottinger Brüel & Kjær, Germany) with a measuring range of ± 25 N were used. During loading, the sample was captured by a 5 Mpx u-Eye camera (IDS, Germany) at a frequency of 20 Hz. The

Figure 1. Samples for mechanical testing. A cylindrical tube cut from V06010L (left), and a specimen for the tensile test cut from SA1802 clamped in the testing machine (right).

dimensional changes in the central region of the specimen were evaluated in real-time in the measurement software TestExpert II 3.5 (Zwick/Roell, Germany) based on images captured on the video-extensometer (edge detection algorithm). The test protocol included five preconditioning cycles, which were performed in a loading interval of 0 - 15 N with a constant crosshead velocity of ± 0.1 mm/s. The loading part of the sixth cycle was used in the theoretical analysis of the constitutive model.

2.3. Inflation experiment

Cylindrical tube pressurizations were carried out by means of an in-house developed inflation-extension setup, which is shown in Figure 2. The configuration of the experiment was vertical. The sample was attached to the cannula using overflow nuts and gaskets. At the top, the sample was attached rigidly. The lower part was movable in order to allow the tube to extend due to the loading pressure (closed tube configuration). Pressure was measured using the KTS Cressto transducer (Cressto, Czech Republic) at a sampling frequency of 100 Hz. The deformation of the sample was determined in the postprocessing of images recorded during the pressurization. The recordings were made using two digital cameras (Basler acA2500, 2592×1944 px., Basler, Germany) placed perpendicular to each other. Sampling rate was 5 Hz. The edge detection algorithm available in the OpenCV library for Python was used in the image analysis of the recordings. The tube elongation was determined from the change in distance of the marks drawn on the tube (Figure 2) and the change in diameter was determined from the contours of the tube. The changes in tube dimensions used in the deformation analysis and constitutive modeling were averaged values from perpendicularly placed cameras. This ensured that any deviations of the tube shape from the assumed circularity would be compensated for. Pressurization was achieved by the motorized syringe. The loading protocol consisted of six preconditioning cycles

Figure 2. Inflation-extension experiments. A scheme of the experimental setup is shown on the left: the sample (1) is pressurized by a piston-driven syringe (2). Pressure is measured using a pressure transducer (3). Two cameras (4,5) record the deformed specimen. The data are gathered and synchronized by a computer (6). A photo of the experimental setup (Middle), and a specimen mounted in the testing chamber (right).

0 – 22 kPa (average speed approx. 1 kPa/s). The loading part of the seventh cycle was used in the subsequent analysis.

2.4. Constitutive model

As ePTFE is a macromolecular material, dissipative processes can be expected to occur during loading. These can be observed as viscoelastic effects (relaxation, creep) or more generally as a dependence of the mechanical response on the loading history. However, our study focuses on the operating state, which in the circulatory system is characterized by long-lasting periodic loading, where the material can be considered as preconditioned, meaning that by repeating a certain deformation history the material exhibits a stable mechanical response without significant viscoelastic effects induced by the deformation history. For this reason, the assumption was made that the investigated ePTFE can be considered as a hyperelastic material, that is, described by the elastic potential W . The constitutive equation of the hyperelastic material can be expressed *via* (1).

$$\mathbf{T} = \frac{\partial W(\mathbf{F})}{\partial \mathbf{F}} - p\mathbf{F}^{-T} \quad (1)$$

Here, \mathbf{T} is the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor and \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient. Since ePTFE is a macromolecular material resembling elastomers, it was also assumed that its mechanical behavior is incompressible (isochoric deformation). Thus, p in (1) is an undetermined multiplier that represents a hydrostatic stress component which does not contribute to W due to the incompressibility constraint, $\det(\mathbf{F}) = 1$, and must be determined from the force boundary condition.

The particular expression of the strain energy density model used in our study is inspired by models commonly used nowadays in vascular biomechanics. The model is given in equation (2) and can be viewed as a member of the family of anisotropic exponential models based on the Holzapfel-Gasser-Ogden model [44].

$$W = \frac{\mu}{2}(I_1 - 3) + \sum_{j=1,4} \frac{k_1^j}{4k_2} (e^{k_2(I_4^j - 1)^2} - 1) \quad (2)$$

In (2), W is expressed as a function of the deformation invariants. The first term corresponds to the isotropic neo-Hookean model and ensures compatibility with classical linear elasticity theory. I_1 is the first principal invariant of the right Cauchy-Green strain tensor \mathbf{C} , $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T\mathbf{F}$, and μ is the stress-like material parameter.

The invariants I_4^j ($j = 1, 4$) are associated with the anisotropy which is assumed to arise from the existence of four preferred directions introduced by the unit material vectors \mathbf{M}^j ($j = 1, 4$). In the material polar cylindrical coordinate system (R, Θ, Z) , these vectors can be expressed as $\mathbf{M}^j = (0, \cos(\beta^j), \sin(\beta^j))^T$. It was assumed that they are aligned with the circumferential direction ($\beta^1 = 0$), longitudinal direction ($\beta^2 = 90^\circ$), and with angle β ($0 < \beta < 90^\circ$) by which two helices symmetrically disposed with respect to the circumferential direction are determined. In other words, $\beta^3 = \beta$, and $\beta^4 = -\beta$. The final expression of invariants is obtained as

$I_4^j = \mathbf{M}^j \cdot \mathbf{C} \mathbf{M}^j$ for $j = 1, 4$. It is clear from (2) that each direction is associated with one stress-like parameter, k_1^j , and one dimensionless parameter, k_2^j . Similarly to Holzapfel et al. [44], it was assumed that helically oriented directions of anisotropy are mechanically equivalent, which in turn gives $k_1^4 = k_1^3$, and $k_2^4 = k_2^3$. It follows that the model has 13 material parameters from which only 8 have to be determined from the experiments ($\mu, k_1^1, k_2^1, k_1^2, k_2^2, k_1^3, k_2^3, \beta$).

The model for the strain energy density function introduced in (2) was used by Baek et al. [45] and by Zeinali-Davarani et al. [46] in their theoretical studies and was successfully employed several times to describe the elasticity of arteries [47–52]. Further details about these models can be found in Holzapfel et al. [44], Gasser et al. [53], or Holzapfel and Ogden [54]. Readers interested in more information on the construction of the invariants used within a description of a material anisotropy can refer to Spencer [55], Holzapfel [56], Itskov [57], or, for example, to Truesdell and Noll [58]. Readers will also find further applications of nonlinear elasticity and modeling of anisotropic behavior in, for example [59–63].

2.5. Model for the uniaxial tensile test

The first Piola-Kirchhoff stress acting in a sample within an uniaxial tensile experiment can be obtained as a ratio of the acting force F to the reference cross-section area A which is expressed in (3). Since an uniaxial stress state is assumed, all other components of the stress tensor are considered to be zero. In (3), the indices k and K indicate the orientation of the sample where $T_{\theta\Theta}$ denotes stress measured in the experiment with the strip aligned with the circumferential direction, whereas T_{ZZ} acts within the uniaxial loading of the strip aligned with the axial direction of the original cylindrical tube.

$$T_{kK}^{\text{EXP}} = \frac{F}{A} \quad (K = \Theta, Z; k = \theta, z) \quad (3)$$

The mechanical stress predicted by the constitutive equation (1) is obtained after the substitution of (2) into (1) and the application of the boundary condition (zero normal stress in an out-of-plane direction). The particular forms of the expressions for $T_{\theta\Theta}$ and T_{ZZ} predicted by the model are in (4) and (5).

$$T_{\theta\Theta}^{\text{MOD}} = \mu\lambda_{\Theta} + k_1^1(I_4^1 - 1)\lambda_{\Theta}e^{k_2^1(I_4^1 - 1)^2} + 2k_1^3(I_4^3 - 1)\lambda_{\Theta}\cos^2(\beta)e^{k_2^3(I_4^3 - 1)^2} - \mu\lambda_{\Theta}^{-3}\lambda_Z^{-2} \quad (4)$$

$$T_{ZZ}^{\text{MOD}} = \mu\lambda_Z + k_1^2(I_4^2 - 1)\lambda_Ze^{k_2^2(I_4^2 - 1)^2} + 2k_1^3(I_4^3 - 1)\lambda_Z\sin^2(\beta)e^{k_2^3(I_4^3 - 1)^2} - \mu\lambda_{\Theta}^{-2}\lambda_Z^{-3} \quad (5)$$

The usual kinematics expected in the central part of the measured specimen in the uniaxial tensile test does not consider shear strain thus \mathbf{F} is diagonal and has the form $\mathbf{F} = \text{diag}[\lambda_R, \lambda_{\Theta}, \lambda_Z]$. Here λ_K ($K = R, \Theta, Z$) are the principal stretches denoted with respect to the material coordinate

system adopted from the initial cylindrical configuration in which the strip was prepared. Due to incompressibility, $\lambda_R = 1/(\lambda_\Theta \lambda_Z)$ holds. Under the above mentioned assumptions, I_4^j ($j=1, \dots, 4$) are given by equations (6).

$$I_4^1 = \lambda_\Theta^2 \quad I_4^2 = \lambda_Z^2 \quad I_4^3 = I_4^4 = \lambda_\Theta^2 \cos^2(\beta) + \lambda_Z^2 \sin^2(\beta) \quad (6)$$

2.6. Model for the inflation and extension of the thin-walled tube

The cylindrical GORE graft specimens were considered to be thin-walled structures, so the Laplace's equation was used to express the equilibrium. The tubes were treated as membranes where only normal stresses, $T_{\theta\Theta}$ and T_{zZ} , act and are constant across the wall thickness. Equation (7) expresses stresses the determined from the experiment.

$$T_{\theta\Theta} = \frac{PR}{H} \quad T_{zZ} = \frac{PR}{2H} \quad (7)$$

Here R and H denote a reference to the middle radius and a reference to thickness, respectively. P is the internal pressure, and mechanical stress is again expressed in the components of the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor. Model predicted stress is, similarly to the tensile experiment, obtained *via* the substitution of (2) into (1) and applying the boundary condition ensuing from the thin-walled character of the sample (zero radial stress). In such a case, the final equations for theoretically predicted stress are given by the same expressions as in the uniaxial tensile experiment, (4) and (5).

Subsequent analysis of the conducted pressurization experiments revealed that ePTFE grafts exhibited a linear response within the range of the physiological loading that was applied. Thus, instead (4) and (5), their linearized counterparts were used in the regression analysis of the inflation behavior. The linearization was conducted with the help of the first order Taylor expansion of (4) and (5) and by adopting a description of the kinematics by means of the engineering strain tensor ε . The final equations are given in (8) and (9).

$$T_{\theta\Theta}^{MOD} = 2(2\mu + k_1^1 + 2k_1^3 \cos^4(\beta))\varepsilon_\Theta + 2(2k_1^3 \cos^2(\beta) \sin^2(\beta) + \mu)\varepsilon_Z \quad (8)$$

$$T_{zZ}^{MOD} = 2(2k_1^3 \cos^2(\beta) \sin^2(\beta) + \mu)\varepsilon_\Theta + 2(2\mu + k_1^2 + 2k_1^3 \sin^4(\beta))\varepsilon_Z \quad (9)$$

Here ε_K ($K = \Theta, Z$) are engineering strain tensor components that are obtained from the principal stretches through $\lambda_K = \varepsilon_K + 1$ ($K = \Theta, Z$).

2.7. Regression analysis of the experiments

The parameters of the constitutive model (2) were estimated by means of the Weighted Least Square method. The applied objective function Q was designed as a combination of the uniaxial tensile experiment Q_{uni} and the pressurization experiment Q_{infl} , thus Q combines the mechanical

response found for the uniaxial stress state and the multi-axial stress state together (10).

$$Q = Q_{uni} + Q_{infl} \quad (10)$$

Q_{uni} was formulated as a sum of the squares of the differences between measured stress (determined by (3)) and stress predicted by the model (equations (4) and (5)) in each direction. Since the videoextensometer in some cases generated artifacts within the measurement of the transverse deformation, instead of a direct substitution of the measured transverse deformation into (4) and (5), it was handled as an unknown and its values were determined by means of a condition of zero transverse stress (uniaxial stress state) in every loading step. Thus, Q_{uni} was handled as a constrained optimization problem. The weighted sum of the squares Q_{uni} is formally expressed in (11). Its minimization was conducted under a simultaneous requirement to satisfy $m+n$ conditions (12) and (13).

$$Q_{uni} = \frac{1}{mT_{\theta\Theta, m}^2} \sum_{i=1}^m (T_{\theta\Theta}^{EXP} - T_{\theta\Theta}^{MOD})_i^2 + \frac{1}{nT_{zZ, m}^2} \sum_{i=1}^n (T_{zZ}^{EXP} - T_{zZ}^{MOD})_i^2 \quad (11)$$

$$T_{zZ, i}^{MOD} = 0 \quad i = 1..m \quad (12)$$

$$T_{\theta\Theta, i}^{MOD} = 0 \quad i = 1..n \quad (13)$$

In (11), $T_{\theta\Theta, m}$ and $T_{zZ, m}$ denote the mean stress achieved in the experiments with circumferential and axial strips and each experiment was described by m and n loading steps.

In regards to the inflation experiment, Q_{infl} was formulated in pressures, (14), which were expressed from both circumferential (7a) and axial (7b) stress acting in the inflated tube. Thus, the pressure predicted by the model can be expressed as in (15) and (16) which is a combination of (7) and (4) and (5). s denotes the number of loading steps and P_m is the mean pressure.

$$Q_{infl} = \frac{1}{sP_m^2} \sum_{i=1}^s \left[(P^{EXP} - P^{\Theta MOD})_i^2 + (P^{EXP} - P^{Z MOD})_i^2 \right] \quad (14)$$

$$P^{\Theta MOD} = T_{\theta\Theta}^{MOD} \frac{H}{R} \quad (15)$$

$$P^{Z MOD} = 2T_{zZ}^{MOD} \frac{H}{R} \quad (16)$$

The objective function (10) was minimized with the help of the NLPsolve procedure available in Maple 2023, which uses a nonlinear sequential quadratic programming method. The whole procedure was conducted in two steps. First, Q_{uni} was minimized separately. Then the whole of Q was minimized by using the parameter estimates from the previous step as starting values. The regression analysis described above was carried out with averaged experimental data.

3. Results

A total of 16 successful tensile tests were performed; 8 with strips cut in the circumferential direction and 8 with strips oriented longitudinally relative to the material cylindrical coordinate system defined for the original GORE vascular substitute. As for the inflation experiment, a total of 5 tubes were successfully pressurized. The mechanical responses to uniaxial tension are displayed in Figure 3 and the results of the inflation-extension behavior are in Figure 4. In both figures, shades of blue are used to depict the longitudinal response (stress-stretch or pressure-stretch) and the data

Results of uniaxial tensile tests and the model prediction

Figure 3. Results of the uniaxial tensile test. The mechanical response of the circumferentially oriented strips is in red, the response of the longitudinal strips is in blue. The data measured in the loading part of the sixth cycle are depicted with thin curves and the averaged responses that were included into the regression analysis are displayed as dots. The mechanical response predicted by the model is depicted by bold curves.

gained in the circumferential direction are depicted with shades of red.

The uniaxial tensile tests suggest a strong material nonlinearity (see Figure 3) although the deformations achieved within the experiment were moderate rather than truly large with regard to how this term is usually used in the context of arterial biomechanics or elastomer mechanics. On the other hand, pressures of up to approx. 20 kPa that can be roughly referred to as physiological loading did not deform the ePTFE grafts to a state that would demonstrate significant nonlinearity (Figure 4). Nevertheless, both the uniaxial tensile test and the inflation experiment show significant anisotropy in the mechanical response of GORE material. In uniaxial tensile loading, the preconditioned material is initially stiffer in the circumferential direction which subsequently changes due to high nonlinearity. Under the multiaxial state of stress that is represented by the pressurization with free axial movement of the closed tube depicted in Figure 4, a stiffer response is demonstrated by the deformation in the axial direction.

The material parameters estimated by means of weighted constrained least-square optimization for the model of the strain energy density function (2) are presented in Table 1. The values of the coefficient of determination R^2 that were calculated separately for each response suggest a good agreement between the observation and the model (see Table 2, $R^2 \in [0.981; 0.999]$). This is particularly true for the

Table 1. Constitutive parameters.

μ [kPa]	k_1^1 [kPa]	k_2^1 [-]	k_1^2 [kPa]	k_2^2 [-]	k_1^3 [kPa]	k_2^3 [-]	β [°]
1750	150	500	6530	499.8	10410	0.02	22.35

Table 2. Coefficients of determination R^2 .

	Uniaxial tension	Pressurization
Circumferential	0.981	0.999
Longitudinal	0.995	0.998

Results of inflation-extension experiments and the model prediction

Figure 4. Results of the pressurization experiment represented in the form of pressure-stretch ratio (left) and stress-stretch ratio (right) relationships. Data (loading part of the seventh cycle) are presented in the same way as in Figure 3 (red = circumferential direction, blue = axial direction, thin lines = data, thick lines = model, and averaged data by symbols).

inflation-extension behavior where the responses presented in Figure 4 show an excellent match between the averaged data and the model.

4. Discussion

Thanks to technological developments, the number of cardiovascular surgeries performed annually has been increasing, as previously fatal conditions can now be treated with modern methods. In 2022, approximately 130 000 bypass surgeries were performed across the EU [64]. Although great progress has been achieved in the development of tissue-engineered vascular grafts, synthetic-material medical devices prevail as the gold standard in many frequently conducted cardiovascular procedures such as large artery reconstruction [14], stent-grafting [21], or coronary and peripheral bypass surgery [4, 5] where an autologous vessel cannot be used. The long-term success of interventions in cardiovascular medicine can be enhanced by the computer-assisted planning of these procedures. This includes, for example, the problem of the optimization of the stent-artery wall interaction, which could determine the minimum pressure necessary for stent expansion in order to ensure sufficient subsequent perfusion while minimizing the arterial injury caused by stent deployment [65–69]. Similarly, engineering-assisted planning based on CFD and FSI analyses can be performed in order to determine the optimal design of the graft or device inserted into the blood stream with the time of minimizing blood shear stress disturbances, or to assess post-implantation stability and the long-term effect of an implanted device on its environment [70, 71]. Much research effort has also been devoted in recent years to, for example, the computational assessment of the risk of abdominal aortic aneurysm rupture [72–77].

However, the reliability of all computational simulations depends significantly on the input parameters. One of the most important is the constitutive model for the biological tissue and for the implant material. While the last few decades have brought great advances in the modeling of the mechanical properties of the arterial wall [44, 53, 78, 79] synthetic grafts have not received such attention, although Dacron vascular grafts have been in clinical use since the 1950s [35]. Partly due to the lack of data on the mechanical properties of prosthetic grafts, researchers often resort to simplifications when dealing with their modeling. The grafts are often assumed to be fully rigid or linearly elastic. However, as shown by Jayendiran et al. [34], choosing a nonlinear-elasticity approach yields significantly different numerical results compared to the simpler models. Drawing on these findings, in this paper anisotropic hyperelasticity was adopted to model Gore-Tex vascular grafts since similar work seems to be missing in the current literature.

Uniaxial tensile experiments with 8 circumferential and 8 longitudinal strips, and 5 pressurization experiments were carried out. Gore-Tex vascular grafts V06010L and SA1802 were used in the mechanical tests, respectively. By choosing these testing methods, it was possible to observe the material within the large uniaxial tension domain, as well as under

multiaxial loads similar to those that can be expected in the circulatory system. The four-fibre family hyperelastic model proposed by Baek [45] as an expansion of the HGO model [44] was used to fit the experimental data. The model was chosen due to its capability of fitting complex anisotropic behavior accompanied by the large strain stiffening known from arterial biomechanics [47]. This model (2) has been successfully used to describe the mechanical response of the human thoracic and abdominal aorta, the common carotid, and the subclavian, renal, common iliac, and femoropopliteal arteries [47–52, 80, 81]. The average stress-stretch curves obtained in a preconditioned state from both types of experiments were fitted by a single set of constitutive parameters. Since the deformations observed in the pressurization were small and the respective mechanical response was linear, a linearized form of the constitutive model was adopted in order to fit the data from this experiment. The linearized constitutive relationships were derived by means of the first order Taylor expansion in the form (8) and (9). The whole optimizing procedure was conducted in two steps where the initial guesses of the parameters were obtained by the separate solving of the least-square problem belonging to the uniaxial experiment. In the second step, the objective function corresponding to the uniaxial tensile experiment and the objective function derived from the inflation-extension experiment were minimized simultaneously. The set of parameter values listed in Table 1 fitted the data well, as evidenced by the coefficients of determination presented in Table 2.

The results of the experiments, as depicted in Figures 3 and 4, show anisotropy of the material under both types of loading. The grafts exhibited a higher circumferential initial stiffness in both experiments. However, an interesting phenomenon can be observed in the uniaxial tension where the longitudinal stiffness increases rapidly, leading to a higher stiffness at deformations of 2% and above, compared to the circumferential direction. A similar behavior of a Gore-Tex graft was documented by Jia et al. [82] who also report a lower initial longitudinal stiffness, which, however, rises more rapidly than the stiffness in the circumferential direction. It may be argued that the same could be expected in the inflation experiment, where the applied pressures are higher. Quite surprisingly, minimal stretches were observed in inflation experiments within a physiological range of internal pressure. The mechanical response was linear as the deformations only reached fractions of percents in both directions.

The linearity of the mechanical response observed in the physiological pressure range could justify the use of a linear model. However, it should be noted that the graft may be subjected to significantly higher loads. This may occur, for example, during stent-graft deployment, during stent-wall interaction, or during subsequent surgical procedures. It is also known that stresses increase locally at the anastomosis site [27, 32, 33]. The aim of our study is to make the resulting model applicable to physiological loads as well as to computer simulations when overloading occurs. If necessary, the linearized form given by equations (8) and (9) can be

used; however, if the stresses and strains exceed the linear range, the general model given by equation (2) is more appropriate.

The overall stiffness of the graft was much higher than that of autologous grafts used, for example, in coronary artery bypass surgery. The mismatch of the mechanical properties of synthetic grafts compared to physiological blood vessels is one of their main drawbacks causing autologous grafts to be the preferred option if available [83, 85]. The difference between the mechanical response of the grafts and of the human great saphenous vein, a vessel frequently used as an autologous replacement, is shown in Figure 5. The stretch-pressure curves for the vein were obtained by simulating the pressurization of the vessel, using the constitutive equation (2) and the Laplace equations (7) to express the pressure-stretch ratio. The constitutive parameter values for the vessel were adopted from Veselý et al. [84] and correspond to the vein of a 60-year-old male. Veselý et al. [84] adopted the HGO model, which is the specialization of (2) received by substituting $k_1^1 = k_2^1 = 0$. The constitutive parameter values employed for the vein are presented in Table 3.

Our study also revealed that different types of ePTFE materials can have significantly different properties. For example, the tested samples were considerably stiffer in uniaxial tension in both directions compared to the Gore-Tex Soft Tissue Patch, as documented by García-García et al. [43]. According to their study, the patches reached deformations exceeding 8% at a true stress of 2 MPa in both directions. In contrast, none of the specimens tested in our study surpassed deformations of 6%, the longitudinal strips only

Figure 5. Comparison of the mechanical response of the Gore-tex graft compared to the human great saphenous vein (GSV) subjected to pressurization.

Table 3. Constitutive parameters of the human great saphenous vein adopted from Veselý et al. [74].

μ [kPa]	k_1^1 [kPa]	k_2^1 [-]	k_1^2 [kPa]	k_2^2 [-]	k_1^3 [kPa]	k_2^3 [-]	β [°]
9.9	0	-	0	-	5.9	62	39.8

reaching around 2% at the given true stress. This could be partly contributed to the fact that no preconditioning was carried out with the samples in the paper by García-García et al. An increase in stiffness could be expected had the pre-cycling been performed, as the same was observed in our experiments. Faturechi et al. [41] who conducted a uniaxial tensile test on a strip of a Gore-Tex vascular graft with preconditioning, recorded behavior similar to that in our study, although the direction in which the specimen was cut is not disclosed in their paper. Finally, it is worth mentioning that the Gore-Tex grafts were stiffer overall than the knitted Dacron grafts as reported in several papers [37, 38, 41, 82]. In any case, the results show that if one wants to obtain reliable input data for computer modeling, it is best to determine a constitutive model for the implanted material directly from the experiments performed with it.

5. Conclusion

Uniaxial tensile and inflation experiments were carried out with samples from Gore-Tex vascular grafts. Preconditioning was performed in both experiments. The pressurization of tubular grafts as well as uniaxial tensile tests of strips cut from the grafts revealed strongly anisotropic behavior. While the grafts were stiffer in the circumferential direction at low stretches, the stiffening in the longitudinal direction was steeper, leading to a higher longitudinal stiffness at deformations of around 2% of elongation in uniaxial tension. The samples behaved nonlinearly within the scope of deformations obtained in uniaxial tensile tests. However, within the range of approximately physiological pressures ($p < 20$ kPa), small stretches and a linear stress-strain response were observed in the inflation tests. An anisotropic, 8-parameter hyperelastic model was used to fit the data from both experiments. The optimized parameter's values resulted in a well-fitting model, making it useful for computational simulations of the graft-vessel interactions.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at <https://zenodo.org> under DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13325101.

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